

Empowering African Librarians: The AfLIA's Role in Enhancing Wikipedia through #1Lib1Ref in Nigeria

Ngozi Perpetua Osuchukwu¹

Department of Library and Information Science
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria
ngostary2k@yahoo.com

Patrick Uzodinma Agwu²

Technical Infrastructure and Digital Services
Kenneth Dike Library
University of Ibadan, Nigeria
uzo123ng@gmail.com

Ifeyinwa Nkechi Okonkwo¹

Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria
zuco609@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://10.5281/zenodo.11110644>

Abstract

Since 2020, AfLIA (African Library and Information Associations and Institutions) has been encouraging librarians across Africa to embrace Wikipedia through the #1Lib1Ref campaign. Sharing knowledge and information is core to the work of librarians, faculty, and other professionals. Wikipedia, with its research and learning tools, provides a valuable platform for this purpose. AfLIA's training programs have empowered Nigerian librarians to become "Wikipedians" and integrate Wikipedia into their work. This study investigated the impact of the #1Lib1Ref campaign in Anambra State, Nigeria. While some academics hesitate to use Wikipedia for research, the study aimed to address these concerns and promote wider acceptance. Focusing on the period 2020-2023, the research explored how AfLIA, the Wikimedia User Group Nigeria (WUGN), and the Igbo Wikimedia User Group created opportunities for Anambra librarians to participate in Wikipedia. The study used a survey design, involving 15 participants from libraries, universities, and other academic institutions in southeast Nigeria. Activities included workshops, training sessions ("edit-a-thons"), and language translation. Data collection methods included focus group discussions, observations, and interviews. Analysis employed a Logical Framework Approach (LFA). The findings revealed that librarians and others joined Wikipedia through AfLIA's #1Lib1Ref campaign in 2020. Training built their capacity to become facilitators, raising awareness and encouraging participation among faculty and other professionals. Over 20 Wikipedia training sessions were held in public libraries and faculties at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, both in-person and online. Participants reported increased knowledge of Wikipedia, its benefits, and its sister projects. This study highlights AfLIA's success in expanding the horizons of African librarians regarding information sharing and collaboration. It emphasizes the importance of continuous learning and new initiatives to ensure the enduring relevance of libraries and librarians in the information age. The research recommends further capacity building and strategies to create strong libraries for the future.

Keywords: 1Lib1Ref, AfLIA, information sharing, librarians, libraries, Wikipedia

Introduction

Libraries and library associations are blending with the changes in the global trend and the futuristic tendencies of information sharing. It is no longer a decision to stay by the fence and look with indifference because the world does not recognize stagnance or people that do not add value. From the developed to the developing world, Wikipedia is making waves and has become one of the most consulted online references in the world by all professionals and groups. Now, the idea of Wikipedia strategy for #lib1ref with the concept of having every librarian in the world adding one reference to Wikipedia moved and became blended. In the words of Biladeau (2017) if every librarian in the world added one citation to Wikipedia, Wikipedia wouldn't have anymore (citation needed) tags. This is the idea that was accepted and spread to all continents. This becomes a tradition for librarians which others outside the profession happily adopt.

Thus, it is out of character for librarians not to come close and seep into the platform that seems to have all the attentions and resources for information sharing. The question of whether Wikipedia has been globally accepted or not is a matter of the mind. What matters is that librarians have embraced the sources, resources, tools and expertise in championing the needed balance in remaining relevance in the world of information. The various Wikipedia engagements in the academic libraries have shown the connections in contributing to knowledge and filling the gaps (Osadebe, Ukwoma, Njoku, Udochukwu, Madumere & Ezeani, 2022). The annual campaign of #lib1ref helps to sustain the information sharing.

It is not an overstatement to mention that Wikipedia and libraries share the same goal and mission. They are both spaces for sharing information just as Ayers (2019) stressed, they both exist to help people who are looking for information, and they both help curate our society's memory and community. It is therefore not surprising that #lib1ref was introduced in Africa by AfLIA to change the library services narrative of information generating and sharing (AfLIA, 2022). The move ushered in strong bonding among the libraries, librarians and the Wikipedia. The librarians are going deeper, amassing great knowledge and even taking the lead in different boards and movement strategies of Wikimedia. There is now linking of data from the Wikimedia to library resources in the libraries.

IFLA in its wisdom recognizes the importance of digital content, collaboration, networking, cultural heritage, engagement and multilingualism which are hinged in Wikimedia projects (Fenoll, Cummings, Tramullas & Hinojo, 2016). This has made Wikimedia to be accepted by the librarians, integrated in the library services and adopted by many library associations as a way to widen access to information and sustainability of library profession. It proves the statement of Bekbalaeva, kyzy, Tumenbaeva and Askhatbekova (2021) that Wikipedia platform has drawn the attention of faculty, librarians, instructional technologists, students, and other stakeholders in the academic community, and many have come to see it as a useful tool in fulfilling their mission. Academic institutions have been known to show interest in teaching with Wikipedia even in secondary schools because of its benefits in enhancing information, media and digital literacies (Konieczny, 2016). These are the focus of equitable quality education which libraries support.

This is about Wikimedia and libraries in Nigeria. It all started in 2020 during the lockdown of covid-19. With the libraries and schools closed, AfLIA shot up with a phrase – #1Lib1Ref and the boredom of sit-at-home became a frenzied activity with new knowledge, new skills, new networking, new collaboration and new ways of dragging communities for new library services. The librarians in Nigeria embraced this nomenclature with dispositions that amazed and amazed till date. In Anambra state, the librarians went further to include the Faculties, community members and all groups, turning them into willing volunteers in telling their own stories while employing media and digital literacies. This study analyzed the insights of the openness and inclusion with the introduction of #1Lib1Ref in the last three years in Nigeria.

Development of #1lib1ref in Anambra, Nigeria

The concept of #1lib1ref brought the initiatives of AfLIA targeted at training Nigerian librarians on Wikipedia. This came at an era when the COVID-19 pandemic was at its peak, coupled with the consequent lock-down with the vast majority outside security and healthcare workers forced to stay at home. Because of the social distancing, the trainings were held online over Zoom, WhatsApp and Google Meet. The project was planned with librarians in mind to enable them participate in the #1lib1ref of 2020. It started with awareness on the new information strategy on the net which attracted sheer interest and inquisition. Then, there was no monetary value attached but personal interest and the need to learn and grow. The librarians were divided into 8 online groups with more experienced colleagues to teach them. A common

whatsapp platform was created for all librarians with the name: Nigerian Wikibraians. Trainings were held regularly and mentoring was extended.

Then, the #1lib1ref campaign came up in May 2020. The librarians were guided to sign up and join the dashboard for the campaign. After the #1lib1ref campaign, Nigerian librarians' interest in Wikipedia piqued, especially, where many of them made it to first 10 and the first 50 editors. Wikipedia began to take roots in the libraries and institutions of learning in Nigeria. The librarians were encouraged to join Wikimedia User Group Nigeria (WUGN) to learn more and access the resources. Soon, they gained more knowledge, started facilitating Wikipedia trainings in the user groups and larger communities. Then the spaces for grants and funding were created and these were approved with resources for Wikipedia projects.

In Anambra state, the Wikipedia projects were approved and the first activity took place at Professor Kenneth Dike State Central e-Library, Awka in May, 2020 with librarians and some community members. After that, more Wikimedia activities and projects picked up in Anambra with more funds. These were held in Book Foundations, Awka, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka and Dunhill Restaurant, Awka. The sister Wikipedia projects were added together with translation of articles to Igbo language. Librarians championed some of these activities and later became Coordinators and leaders of these hubs and Network in Anambra State. The Faculties in Nnamdi Azikiwe University were sensitized and different workshops were held for the lecturers and the library staff while certificates were issued to participants. These improved the connection and collaborations among the librarians, Faculties and the Wikimedia communities. The students from various faculties joined in the training and the awareness of #1lib1ref increased.

Thus, the #1lib1ref of 2021 and 2022 became general campaigns and activism not only for librarians again but for Faculty members, students and community members in Anambra. Funds and grants for #1lib1ref were granted by Wikimedia User Group Nigeria (WUGN) and Ig wikimedians Group. Prizes, gifts and certificates were given to highest contributors and translators at each year's campaign. #1lib1ref has become a celebrated campaign in Nigeria with ample preparations and strategies. The campaign inspires librarians and non-librarians in creating and improving articles, adding authentic and accurate resources as well as translation of articles.

Statement of the problem

Librarians have always played a key role in information access and creation. Today, the information world revolves around digital tools and media. However, library services can sometimes seem outdated and undervalued. Librarians risk becoming irrelevant if they don't adapt to these trends. The #1lib1ref initiative by AfLIA in Nigeria is a great example of embracing global digital practices in libraries. Sharing best practices helps librarians worldwide stay relevant and provide excellent information services. Librarians need to be quick to adopt new trends and guide users towards contributing their own cultural knowledge. This study investigated the impact of the #1lib1ref initiative in Anambra State, Nigeria. It specifically looked at librarians and faculty members participation in Wikipedia projects to assess the program's usefulness. The following pages will present the study's findings

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to analyse the AfLIA's connection that stimulated the embrace of Wikipedia with #1Lib1Ref among the librarians and the Faculties in Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study:

1. Highlighted the #1Lib1Ref campaign among the librarians and the Faculties in Anambra, Nigeria
2. Identified the Wikipedia activities implemented in Anambra State, Nigeria from 2020 to 2023
3. Examined the Wikipedia spaces created for inclusion of librarians and the Faculties in Anambra
4. Looked at the perception of Wikipedia editors in Anambra
5. Harness the prospects of contributing to Wikipedia platforms

Literature review

The Library and Wikipedia

Librarians are stepping out to identify the relevant fields that define their nature and terms of existence. One of such fields is Wikipedia with its sister projects. Wikipedia comes in a well packaged box that fits into all the features libraries exhude. For instance it cares about relevant references that must be accurate and authenetic, information that must be factual devoid of misinformation, disinformatio, malinformation and fake news. The important roles librarians

play matches the goals of Wikipedia in many ways as Wikipedia also has spaces for Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) outreach strategy (GLAM), outreaches among others (Biladeau, 2017). This has made librarians realize that remaining relevant with new tools and platforms will widen their knowledge, create collaborate with other players in the information sectors, create more accessible platforms for their users and involve their communities. The connection with the libraries, librarians and Wikimedia has long become a feasible integration that ensures the provision and accessibilities of free resources for editors (OCLC, 2023; Kumar, 2019; Fenoll, Cummings, Tramullas & Hinojo, 2016).

Activities of #1Lib1Ref campaign

Undoubtedly, the concept of #1Lib1Ref has widened the scope of librarians in information, media and digital literacies. The #1lib1ref has exposed librarians to improving digital articles, editathons, digitization of content, Wikipedia in Residence, data-a-thon and content creators (Stakić, Popovic & Krinulović, 2021). This is a huge point that made many libraries and librarians plan and organize activities on #1lib1ref. The Marx Library's #1Lib1Ref campaign of University of South Alabama citation workshop taught the librarians how to add references and citations (University of South Alabama, 2016). In 2020 the Israeli librarians organized #1lib1ref competition that resulted in 4,700 edits with updating Wikipedia articles with authentic references (Library Learning Spaces, 2023). The activities of #1lib1ref among the librarians also stretched to library associations that opened spaces for their members to learn. For instance AfLIA has organized many workshops on #1lib1ref and other courses for African librarians (AfLIA, 2022). The Ist Cohort of WikiAfLIB produced librarians who are among the leading experts in Wikipedia, today. The modules and courses taught deepened the knowledge on adding references, creating articles, fixing typos among others (Osuchukwu, Godwin, Ebijuwa, Ikenna and Olabisi, 2022).

Apart from #1lib1ref, many libraries and librarians have planned and implemented activities on edit-a-thon. Bridges and Dowell (2020) reported in a study that academic libraries such as MIT in the US, National Autonomous University in Mexico, Oxford University in England, and Universidade de São Paulo in Brazil have extensive experience hosting editathons. Librarians have also integrated Wikipedia in the classroom for students learning in the right use of references, building digital contents and preventing plagiarism (Ukwoma, Osadebe, Okafor, & Ezeani, 2021; Oliver, 2015). Other libraries have joined in the initiatives of Wikipedia activities. The University Library, Svetozar Marković in Belgrade, Serbia, 2015

collaborated with the Faculty of Mathematics of the University of Belgrade and Wikimedia Serbia and successfully ran a project till 2016. Their activity enhanced on the open access and open education, OA software, digital repositories and valuable sources of information which were made available in Wikipedia (Popovic, Antonic, Krinulovic & Stakić, 2016).

Again, the Wikimedia+Libraries International Convention 2022 in Maynooth increased the librarians' learning and insight on Wikipedia and its connection with information networking (Andersdotter, 2022). This was supported by WMF. In the same vein, librarians in Spain organized a Wikipedia event with partnerships with local Wikimedia chapters where Wikidata, Wikisource, and other Wikipedia sister projects were held (Bridges & Llebot, 2021). This activity produced upload of photos to Wikimedia Commons, identifying gaps in Wikipedia content and filling those gaps, transcribing historic documents and adding them to Wikisource. Indeed Wikipedia cares about cultural heritage and indigenous knowledge which also accommodates translation of local languages for global view. It supports data and photo of any information for emphasis.

The spaces created for the inclusion of the faculties and professionals in Anambra State

Wikipedia and Libraries in Nigeria is becoming a Powerful Partnership for Knowledge sharing and creation. Research shows that Wikipedia can be a valuable tool in academic settings, and libraries play a key role in this. Both Wikipedia and libraries share a mission of expanding access to knowledge. They achieve this by creating high-quality academic and research content for educational use (Kumar, 2020). Libraries take the initiative to organize Wikipedia editing events for faculty, students, and the broader academic community (Osadebe et al., 2022). This participation benefits everyone:

Increased Visibility: Libraries can showcase their relevance and value by helping scholars contribute to Wikipedia.

Inclusive Growth: Wikipedia promotes participation and the creation of new knowledge.

Funding Opportunities: The #1lib1ref program even opens doors to grants and funding for non-librarians who organize Wikipedia editing events.

This collaboration between Wikipedia and Nigerian librarians is a win-win. It empowers faculty members to contribute their expertise and strengthens the relationship between libraries and the academic community.

The perception

Several studies have examined the perception of faculties in teaching with Wikimedia. Konieczny, (2016) explored the current perception of Wikipedia in academia, focusing on both the reasons for its unpopularity among some and the reasons for its growing acceptance among others. The analysis showed some acceptance, some not very sure of its stand because of some misconceptions on using Wikimedia in the academics. Whether or not if Wikipedia is acceptable has changed to a massive acknowledgement of openness of resources, cultural heritage and unrestrained knowledge (Ziku, Fabos, Dangerfield, Moe & Osuchukwu, 2023; Ford, 2016). Indeed, the perception of distrust and lack of confidence in Wikipedia by the academic community have been reported (Jemielniak & Aibar 2016). The notion shows the warning of some academic staff on their students on not to use Wikipedia for scholarly writing.

Prospects of contributing to Wikipedia platforms

Obviously, there is more to learn about Wikipedia as it is very vast. So far, the user communities, the hubs and the libraries have continued to work on the strategies for developing more activities and tools for learning. A show of prospect revealed OCLC(2023) in 2018 being tied between US public libraries and English Wikipedia. The goal was to connect the library staff with Wikipedia to enable linking of learning resources and activities in the services to the communities. There are also training prospect in building the capacities of libraries which Stakić, Popovic and Krinulović (2021) reported in a multi-year project to train librarians and students of librarianship and information science to use wiki tools, including writing articles on Wikipedia at the the University Library “Svetozar Marković”. The project which has been supported by Wikimedia Serbia and has been ongoing since 2015. This enunciated the long term relationship signifying good prospects between Wikipedia and the libraries for more knowledge sharing.

Methodology

This was a survey research design that spanned Wikipedia projects from 2020-2022 in Nigeria. The area of the study was Anambra State in the South-East, Nigeria. The population of the study was fifteen, made up of librarians, professors and all cadres in academia in Anambra state. The instruments used were Focus group discussion, observation, and interviews. The discussions were recorded and documented during the meet-up at Prof Ken Dike State Central e-Library, Awka. The activities of the study were powered by Wikimedia User Group Nigeria (WUGN) and Ig Wikimedian User Group. Over 20 Wikipedia projects took place in Anambra

in Nnamdi Azikiwe Awka, Professor Kenneth Dike State Central Library, Awka and Book Foundation Awka under the grant application by librarians. These included facilitation, article creation and fixing typos, building accurate references, edit-a-thon and language translation. The results were presented with Logical framework analysis (LFA) and simple percentages

Findings

Table 1: The #1Lib1Ref campaign in Anambra, Nigeria from 2020 to 2022

S/N	#1Lib1Ref Campaign	Venue	No of activities	Participants	Year	Remark
1.	Awareness and training on #1lib1ref	Prof. Kenneth Dike State Central e-Library	1	15 Librarians	May, 2020	Facilitated by librarians
2.	1lib1ref outreach in Anambra state	Book Foundation Awka	1	32 librarians and non-librarians	August, 2022	Facilitated by librarians
3.	1lib1ref cite-a-thon	Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka	1	21 librarians and non-librarians	June 2021	Facilitated by librarians

The findings showed that the #1Lib1Ref campaigns took place in Anambra, Nigeria in 2020 at Prof. Kenneth Dike State Central e-Library, facilitated by the librarians. Also in Book Foundation Awka in 2021 and 2022, respectively. This shows that awareness and successful sensitization were carried out in Anambra with #1lib1ref that brought librarians and faculties into Wikipedia.

Table 2a: Identification of Wikipedia activities that included the librarians and the Faculties in Anambra, Nigeria from 2020 to 2023.

	Wikipedia activities	Venue	Editors	Year	Remark
--	----------------------	-------	---------	------	--------

1.	1lib1ref outreach in Anambra state 1lib1ref cite-a-thon Awareness and training on #1lib1ref	Book Foundation Awka Book Foundation Awka Online Prof. Ken Dike State Central e-Library Awka	32 21 15	August, 2022 June, 2021 May, 2020	Training and edit-a-thon
2.	Translate English articles to Igbo	Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka; Book Foundation Awka Online	33	October, 2022	Training and Data-a-thon
3.	Translate Wikidata properties to Igbo language	Book Foundation Awka Online	31	August, 2022	Training and Data-a-thon
4.	Introduction to WikiSource: A Basic WikiSource Training and Edit-a-thon	Book Foundation Awka	24	February, 2023	Training and edit-a-thon
5.	Wikipedia edit-a-thon	Prof. Ken Dike State Central e-Library Awka; Book Foundation Awka, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Dunhill Restaurant, Awka	Series of events	May 2020 to 2023	Trainig, edit-a-thon and contests
6.	Wikicommons	Book Foundation Awka	10	2022	Training, photo upload to wikicommons
7.	Climate change Awareness	Dunhill Restaurant, Awka	27	December, 2022-2023	Ongoing training and edit-a-thon
8.	World Cancer Day 2023	Dunhill Restaurant, Awka	23	February, 2023	Training, awareness, edit-a-thon and contest
9.	Bridging Misinformation and Disinformation in Nigeria election and Politics	Dunhill Restaurant, Awka	20	February, 2023	Training and edit-a-thon
10	Africa Youth Month 2022 in Wikipedia Anambra Network	Online	14	November - December, 2022	Training, edit-a-thon and contest

Table 2b: Identification of Wikipedia activities that included the librarians and the Faculties in Anambra, Nigeria from 2020 to 2022

S/N	Wikipedia activities	Venue	Editor d	Year	Remark
11	Opening up Knowledge about Anambra Senatorial Zone	Book Foundation, Awka	32	November - December, 2022	Training and edit-a-thon and contest
12	Lexicographical Data and 10th Birthday of Wikidata	Dunhill Restaurant Awka	30	October 2022	Training and edit-a-thon
13	Outreach awareness and edit-a-thon at Nnamdi Azikiwe University in Awka	Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka and Online	141	September - November, 2022	Training and edit-a-thon
14	Wiki Loves Names	Book Foundation, Awka	54	September, 2022	Training, edit-a-thon and contest
15	An introduction to Wikidata lexemes	Book Foundation, Awka	39	September -October, 2022	Training and edit-a-thon
16	Databox edit-a-thon, improve articles on the Igbo Wikipedia	Book Foundation, Awka Online	29	August, 2022	Training, edit-a-thon and contest
17	Igbo Wikimedians User Group Int'l Labour Day Akaoru Ndi Igbo Edit a thon	Caso-Wisdom Tech, Onitsha	5	May, 2021	Training, edit-a-thon and contest
18	Igbo Wikimedians User Group, Awka Wikipedia Training Edit a thon	Prof. Ken Dike State Central e-Library, Awka	19	March-April, 2021	Training, edit-a-thon and contest
19	South-East Training of Trainees	Book Foundation, Awka	15	September, 2022	Training
20	Inauguration of Anambra Wikimedia Network	Book Foundation, Awka	45	September, 2022	Inauguration

Tables 2a and 2b show twenty (20) fully funded Wikipedia training held in Anambra after the wake by #lib1ref in 2020 at public libraries and the Faculties in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria. It also shows the in-person and online modes activities. Participants' capacities

were built and they became facilitators, bringing the Faculties and other professionals via information sharing and awareness creation.

Table 3: Examine the spaces created for inclusion of librarians from Anambra into Wikipedia

S/N	Wikipedia Spaces created	Location	Funder/Grantor	Number	Year	Remark
1.	Funds and grants	In-person and online	Wikimedia User Group Nigeria, Ig Wikimedians User Group, Wikimedia Foundations	Over 20	2020 - 2023	Training on Edit-a-thon, upload of photos, translation, article creation and adding citations
2.	Fully sponsored workshops	Lagos Awka	Wikimedia User Group Nigeria	1 3	March 2022 Aug. 2022	Capacity building workshop on human trafficking & edit-a-thon
3.	Fully sponsored Wikimania Conf. in Lagos	Lagos	Wikimedia User Group Nigeria	3	Aug. 2022	Global Wikimania conference and sharing
4.	Coordinators: Wikimedia Anambra Network Ig Wikibrarians & Unizik Hubs	Awka	Wikimedia User Group Nigeria Igbo Wikimedians User Group	3	Sept, 2022 2021 2022	Coordinators of the 3 hubs and Networks are Librarians. They plan, sensitize and organize activities for Wikimedia
5.	WikiIndaba	Rwanda Online	Wikimedia Foundations	1 1	2022 2022	Full scholarship for participation.
6.	Libraries+Wikipedia Conference	Dublin	Wikimedia Foundations	3	July 2022	Wikibrarians conf. for learning & sharing
7.	Presentation of Wikipedia papers	IFLA 2022, Wikimania, Lagos Dublin	Individual Individual WUGN WMF	4	2022	Sharing and contributing to knowledge on Wikipedia projects

8.	Publication of Wikipedia researches	IGI Global IFLA Lib. Book Chapters	Individual	3	2022 and 2023	Sharing and contributing to knowledge on Wikipedia projects
----	-------------------------------------	------------------------------------	------------	---	---------------	---

Table 3 shows that librarians have received funds/grants from Wikimedia User Group Nigeria, Ig Wikimedians User Group and Wikimedia Foundations to organize activities and projects from 2020 – date. They have also been fully sponsored to workshops, conferences in and outside Nigeria. There are also librarians from Anambra that lead and coordinate hubs, communities and networks. researchers in Wikimedia, article creators and improvement, quality references, Wikipedia facilitators, link data experts and digital photographers.

The observation of librarians' activities also showed great enthusiasm in Wikipedia contests as they made effort to edit volumes of articles with accurate sources. They also applied for funds, sought for scholarship and contribute actively in the user groups.

Table 4: Perceptions of Wikipedia in Anambra, Nigeria

S/N	Items	Agree	Undecided	Disagree
1.	Enhances media and information literacies	15		
2.	Shares the same objectives with libraries	12	3	
3.	Potentials for increased information services	13	2	
4.	Builds network and connection with peers	10	5	
5.	Removes boredom	10	3	2
6.	Good practices for libraries engagement	15		
7.	Good platform for research	8	5	2
8.	Increases online visibility	13	2	
9.	Can increase library patronage	13	2	
10.	Good platform for telling our stories	14	1	
11.	A whole new information platform	15		

The Table on perception shows that the participants agreed fully on Wikipedia enhancing, media and digital literacies, forms good practices for libraries' engagement, viewed it as a whole new information and good platform for telling their own stories. Also agreed on were that Wikipedia can increase, online visibility as well as increase

library patronage and information services. The perception on viewing Wikipedia as a good research platform rated undecided and disagreement.

Interview further revealed that the academic scholarship still has its reservation on Wikipedia and they stand with that. Hence, the perception on Wikipedia agrees on the good benefits of greater insights in the world of knowledge.

Prospects of contributing to Wikipedia platforms

From the FGD and interview, the participants stated that:

“Wikipedia can improve information services and make libraries to remain relevant. This is the kind of new services people want.”

“If other people in other professions are doing it, then librarians and those in the academia cannot be joking about it. Libraries can use it to link their library resources and build data. I heard it is possible. We can learn it.”

“The Wikipedia grants will be helpful in boosting library activities on cultural heritage.”

“This can connect us with other Wikipedians and bring collaboration for ,ore learning.”

“We can ask for library-related projects that can excel our services.”

Discussion of findings

The result on the #1Lib1Ref campaign which included the librarians and members of the Faculties indicated the level of its awareness and the bonding Wikipedia attracts. The fact the #1lib1ref happened in three different places in Anambra showed its extension of including everyone to be part of this campaign that exposes people to learn improving digital articles, editathons, digitization of content, data-a-thon and content creators (Stakić, Popovic & Krinulović, 2021). These are scholarly activities needed by all players in the academic environment to contribute to knowledge while avoiding plagiarisms as Ukwoma, Osadebe, Okafor, & Ezeani (2021) noted.

The revelation of over twenty activities and projects carried out in Anambra State after the introduction of #1lib1ref indicated that learning of Wikipedia took place as well as adding values. In less than four years, librarians have mastered the platform, leading facilitations in different locations and documenting their reports on meta. This is power and acknowledgement of every AfLIA's efforts in streaming Wikimedia in Nigeria (AfLIA, 2022). The courses paid off with many Wikimedia applications answered.

That librarians stepped into the gracious spaces created, showed acceptance and acknowledgement of Wikimedia. It rhymes with the notions of OCLC, (2023) and Kumar (2019) that integration of Wikimedia would ensure provision and accessibilities of free resources for editors. These are the benefits many librarians are already reaping by editing Wikipedia articles.

Clearly, the discussions on the perception and prospects showed the mindset, prompt and demeanour of librarians towards Wikipedia. There seems to be slight reservation on some librarians which shows they might not have understood it all. Wikipedia is huge and needs time to process it. However, the general consensus that it has great potentials for libraries information sharing looks like librarians have hit the gold mine with Wikipedia. Their best is yet to be seen while navigating all Wikipedia strategies.

Implication of the study

The study shows that Wikipedia can enhance information services and build capacities of the editors. Although, it is just a little above three years in Anambra State, it is important that capacity building is extended to teach more people in the libraries, academic environment and the communities. This will help make library and information services easier. If librarians who should be in the forefront of all information platforms and strategies are still deciding whether to adopt Wikipedia or not while others take a large chunk, they will be doing themselves great disservice. Today's knowledge does not respect boundaries or professional claims. What it knows is who has it and where it happens. All perceptions should gear towards advancement of future services to avoid being swept away by people on the fast lane.

Conclusion

The analysis of #lib1ref in Anambra State, Nigeria is a whole new insight that needs further studies. The learning and building of knowledge with astute participation on Wikipedia platforms show expertise, willingness and readiness to explore more. Thus, this study concluded that:

- a) The awareness and sensitization on #lib1ref created the opening for Wikipedia for librarians and the Faculty members in Anambra state, Nigeria.
- b) The various Wikipedia activities carried out are evidences of knowledge gained
- c) Spaces created for the librarians to move further into the Wikipedia programs are embraced and valued critically
- d) The perception and prospects are good measures of evaluation which can get better with more understanding

Recommendation

The following recommendations were made:

- a) More awareness and sensitization are needed in other areas and institutions of learning in Anambra State
- b) There should be more activities on other Wikipedia sisters projects. They are still silent in Anambra State
- c) More librarians should work hard to gain more scholarships and grants to expand their horizon and information services for the better
- d) Enlightenment can go on to allay the fears and build confidences of those who have little knowledge of Wikipedia strategies

References

- AfLIA (2022). Introducing champions for the 3rd African Librarians Week 1Lib1Ref campaign. Retrieved on 27th February, 2023 from <https://web.aflia.net/introducing-champions-for-the-3rd-african-librarians-week-1lib1ref-campaign/>
- Andersdotter, K. (2022). Wikimedia+Libraries International convention 2022 in Maynooth. Retrieved on 27th February, 2023 from <https://karolina.andersdotter.cc/2022/08/wikimedialibraries-international-convention-2022-in-maynooth/>
- Ayers, P. (2019). Wikipedia and libraries. Retrieved on 23rd February 2023 from <https://wikipedia20.mitpress.mit.edu/pub/vj43a02q/release/16>
- Bekbalaeva, J., kyzy, A. N, Tumenbaeva, S. & Askhatbekova, Z. (2021). Chapter 1: Library-faculty collaboration using Wikipedia for learning and civic engagement. In Bridges, L. M., Pun, R. & Arteaga, R. A. *Wikipedia and Academic Libraries: A Global Project*. Maize Books, 5-17
- Biladeau, S. (2017). Wikipedia's 2018 #1lib1ref campaign. Retrieved on 26th February, 2023 from <https://libraries.idaho.gov/wikipedias-2018-1lib1ref-campaign/>
- Bridges, L., & Llebot, C. (2021). Librarians as Wikimedia movement organizers in Spain: An interpretive inquiry exploring activities and motivations. *First Monday*, 26(6/7) 1-29 <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v26i3.11482>
- Bridges, L.M., & Dowell, M. (2020). A perspective on Wikipedia: Approaches for Educational Use. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 46(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2019.102090>
- Fenoll, C., Cummings, J., Tramullas, J., & Hinojo, À. (2016). Opportunities for public libraries and Wikipedia. Retrieved on 12 February, 2023 from <https://www.ifla.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/assets/hq/topics/info-society/iflawikipediaandpubliclibraries.pdf>
- Ford, H. (2016). Wikipedia and the sum of all human Information. *Nordisk Tidsskrift for Informationsvidenskab og Kulturformidling*, 5 (1) 9-13
- Jemielniak, Dariusz, and Eduard Aibar. 2016. "Bridging the gap between wikipedia and academia." *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* 67 (7): 1773–1776. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23691>
- Konieczny, P. (2016). Teaching with Wikipedia in a 21st -century classroom: Perceptions of Wikipedia and its educational benefits. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67(7), 1-59 (preprint) DOI: [10.1002/asi.23616](https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23616)
- Kumar, V. (2020). Role of libraries in Wikipedia content development. Retrieved on 23rd February 2020 from <http://eprints.rclis.org/40410/1/Role%20of%20libraries%20in%20Wikipedia%20content%20development-full-text.pdf>
- Library Learning Spaces (2023). Israeli librarians win the #1Lib1Ref Wikipedia campaign. Retrieved on 26th February, 2023 from <https://librarylearningspace.com/israeli-librarians-win-1lib1ref-wikipedia-campaign/>
- OCLC (2023). Wikipedia+Libraries: Better together. Retrieved on 23rd February 2020 from <https://www.webjunction.org/explore-topics/wikipedia-libraries.html>
- Oliver, J. T. (2015). One-shot Wikipedia: An edit-sprint toward information literacy. *Reference Services Review* 43(1):81-97

- Popovic, A., Antonic, S., Krinulovic, O. and Stakić, D. (2016). Open science on Wikipedia: Libraries' activities in Serbia. Paper presented at the 2nd Annual Conference on Professional Information Resources, May 24-25 at Prague. <https://www.inforum.cz/proceedings/2016/25/>
- Osadebe, N. E., Ukwoma, S. C. Dr; Njoku, E. O., Udochukwu, Madumere, C. P. & Ezeani, C. N. (2022). Wikipedia edit-a-thon in a Nigerian academic library. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 7231. Retrieved on 27th February, 2023 from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7231>
- Osuchukwu, N. P., Godwin, N. G., Ebijuwa, A. S., Ikenna, G. T. and Olabisi, O. S. (2022). Chapter 1: Integrating Wikipedia in the information service space: The WikiAflib experience. In Innocent Isa Ekoja, Esoswo Francisca Ogbomo and Omorodion Okuonghae. *handbook of research on emerging trends and technologies in librarianship*. IGI Global Book. DOI: 10.4018/978-1-7998-9094-2.ch001. <https://www.igi-global.com/book/handbook-research-emerging-trends-technologies/275605>
- Popovic, A., Antonic, S., Krinulovic, O. and Stakić, D. (2016). Open science on Wikipedia: Libraries' activities in Serbia. Paper presented at the 22nd Annual Conference on Professional Information Resources at Prague. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311935359_Open_Science_on_Wikipedia_Libraries'_Activities_in_Serbia
- Stakić, D., Popovic, A. and Krinulović, O. (2021). Wiki-Librarian : A project to train librarians and students to work with Wikipedia. *Infotheca - Journal for Digital Humanities* 21(1), 55-72. DOI: [10.18485/infotheca.2021.21.1.3](https://doi.org/10.18485/infotheca.2021.21.1.3).
- Ukwoma, S.C., Osadebe, N.E., Okafor, V.N. and Ezeani, C.N. (2021). "Unveiling the veiled: Wikipedia collaborating with academic libraries in Africa in creating visibility for African women through Art+Feminism Wikipedia edit-a-thon", *Digital Library Perspectives*, 37 (4), 449-462. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DLP-08-2020-0079>
- University of South Alabama (2016). #1Lib1Ref Wikipedia citation campaign: How to participate. Retrieved on 26th February, 2023 from <https://libguides.southalabama.edu/c.php?g=611798&p=4253187>
- Ziku, M., Fabos, B., Dangerfield, M. C., Moe, J. & Osuchukwu, N. P. (2023). Digital community heritage and open access: Report of the creative commons open culture working group [presentation]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7539227>